

ON THE PREPARATION OF 7-METHYL-3-HYDROXYTHIO-NAPHTHENE AND ITS CONDENSATION WITH ISATIN.

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7-Methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene has been prepared and condensed with isatin. 3-Indole-2'-(7'-methyl)-thionaphtheneindigo, thus obtained, has been compared with its isomeric 4', 5', and 6'-methyl derivatives, prepared before by the present author and also the parent compound, Thioindigo Scarlet R.

It appears that 7-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene has not yet been described in literature although the possibility of obtaining its oxidation product, 7:7'-dimethylthioindigo, starting from *o*-toluidine, has been mentioned in D. R. P. 241910 which does not give any particulars regarding its preparation and properties (*cf.* Thorpe and Ingold, "Vat Colours," 1923, p. 129).

The present author required 7-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene, in order to complete the study of indole-methylthionaphtheneindigos, methylthionaphthene - acenaphthyleneindigos, bismethylthionaphtheneethyleneindigos, and benzylidenemethylthionaphthenes (Guha and Basu-Mallick, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, **11**, 395 ; Guha, *ibid.*, 1937, **14**, 240 ; 1938, **15**, 501 ; 1933, **10**, 679 ; 1936, **13**, 94 ; 1938, **15**, 20 ; 1935, **12**, 659 ; 1937, **14**, 709 ; 1938, **15**, 359 ; *cf.* Auwers and Arndt, *Ber.*, 1909, **42**, 551). It has been obtained from *o*-methylphenylthioglycollic acid by the action of phosphorus pentoxide by following the method of preparation of 5-chloro-3-hydroxythionaphthene (D. R. P. 224567 ; Friedlander, **10**, 474 ; *cf.* Auwers and Thies, *Ber.*, 1920, **53**, 2285). The isolation of this substance has made the path open and easy for the synthesis of a large number of valuable thioindigoid vat dyes in the isatin, acenaphthenequinone, phenanthrenequinone, conjugated indigo analogues and thioindogenide series just in the same way as already described by the present author in the case of 4-, 5-, and 6-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene (Guha, *loc. cit.*; Guha and Basu-Mallick ; *loc. cit.*) and also in other series by several other workers (F. P. 693903 ; *Chem. Zentr.*, 1931, **I**, **102**, 2944 ; U. S. P., 1850758, *Chem. Zentr.*, 1932, **103**, **II**, 1374 ; *Ber.*, 1914, **47**, 955 ; 1923, **56**, 1308 ; 1925, **58**, 824 ; *Annalen*, 1925, **443**, 211).

When isatin is condensed with 7-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene, 3-indole-2'-(7'-methyl)-thionaphtheneindigo (I, R = Me) is obtained.

Its colour and dyeing properties have been studied. The absorption spectra has been taken in xylene solution. The microphotogram (Fig. 1) has been drawn and the absorption maxima calculated from the graph. It is found (*cf.* Table I) that this 7'-methyl dye is lighter than the parent compound, commercially known as Thioindigo Scarlet R (I, R=H), *i.e.*, when the Me group is introduced into the *ortho* position to the indigo auxochrome S, the colour of the mother substance is lightened. This effect of the influence of the Me group in the 7'-position, which has been studied for the first time now, and also the effect of the Me group in the 4'-, 5'-and 6'- positions (Guha, *loc. cit.*) has enabled the author to generalise that when the Me group is introduced in the 4'-, 6'- and 7'-positions, the colour of the parent compound is lightened, and when the same group occupies the 5'-position the colour of the mother substances is deepened; *i.e.*, lightening and deepening of colour of the mother substance take place alternately as the Me group is shifted from the 4'- to the 6'-position and it is further lightened when the same group is again shifted from the 6'- to the 7'-position of the thionaphthene nucleus of the molecule of 3-indole-2'-thionaphtheneindigo (I, R=H).

The absorption maxima of 3-indole 2'-thionaphtheneindigo and its four theoretically possible isomeric methyl derivatives, having the Me group in the thionaphthene nucleus of the molecule, are given in Table I for comparison.

TABLE I.

T=Thionaphtheneindigo.		Absorption maxima.
Compounds.		
3-Indole-2'-T	...	4892 Å
3-Indole-2'-(4'-Me)-T	...	4885
3-Indole-2'-(5'-Me)-T	...	4986
3-Indole-2'-(6'-Me)-T	...	4880
3-Indole-2'-(7'-Me)-T	...	4848

A detailed study of this class of dyes in various series has been undertaken.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

7-Methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene.—*o*-Methylphenylthioglycollic acid (10 g.) was heated in a hard glass test tube in an oil-bath at 150°. To the molten substance, phosphorus pentoxide (15 g.) was added, and the mixture stirred well for 1 hour at 150-160°, and allowed to cool. The hard mass was digested well with sodium hydroxide (2*N* approx) and the resulting solution acidified with hydrochloric acid, 7-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene being removed by distilling in steam. It was collected as a colourless heavy oily liquid which turned pale yellow. By allowing it to stand in ice, the oily substance solidified which was at first dried in a vacuum desiccator and finally on a porous plate, when it became colourless, m. p. 68-69°. It is a rectangular crystalline substance, soluble in pyridine, nitrobenzene, aniline, acetic acid, alcohol and ether. (Found: S, 19.41. C₉H₈OS requires S, 19.51 per cent).

3-Indole-2'-(7'-methyl)-thionaphtheneindigo.—The dark red solution, produced by boiling isatin (0.574 g.) and 7-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.641 g.) in 43 c.c. of glacial acetic acid and 4 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid for 15-20 minutes, was allowed to stand overnight. The deep red crystalline precipitate was collected and crystallised from xylene in bundles of long silky bright scarlet needles or from alcohol in dark red needles, m.p. 314°. It is soluble in acetic acid, alcohol and difficultly soluble

FIG. 1.

Curves 1 and 2 refer to 3-indole-2'-(7'-methyl)-thionaphtheneindigo ; corresponding exposure being (1) 15' and (2) 20' respectively.

in xylene. Cold concentrated sulphuric acid dissolves it with a dark brown colour but the solution in hot concentrated sulphuric acid is green. It dyes wool in dark red shade from an acid bath and cotton in light red colour from a light yellow alkaline hydrosulphite vat. (Found: S, 11.04. $C_{17}H_{11}O_2NS$ requires S, 10.92 per cent).

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